
D2.2 Report on the Procedure for Updating Priority Topics

WP2 Integrative Strategic Research Agenda

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: UCM, SSI, ISS, IP, Anses,
BfR, SVA, INSA, UoS, CODA-CERVA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Report on the procedure for updating of priority topics

Objectives

1. To identify priority research and integrative topics in the domains of foodborne zoonoses (FBZ), antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and emerging threats (ET).
2. To develop the strategic research agenda (SRA).

1. Gap analysis of the first round projects

(February 2018 - April 2018)

- Objectives of the gap analysis:
 - To identify priority research and integrative topics that are insufficiently covered by the first round of granted projects. Topics that are sufficiently covered will then be excluded from the second call for project proposals.
 - To identify research areas in the SRA insufficiently covered by the first round of granted projects.
 - To assess whether stakeholders' needs identified in WP5 are already covered by first round projects.
- Development of an assessment procedure and criteria to be used by the domain and theme secretaries to identify gaps in the coverage of the topics or in the SRA. The assessment procedure and criteria will be prepared by the WP2 team in consultation with the secretaries. The assessment will then be performed by the secretaries and their assessments will be analysed by the WP2 team.
- A consensus meeting with the domain and theme secretaries and WP2 team will be held in April 2018 at Schiphol Airport (see point 2) to present and discuss the results of the gap analysis. Each secretary will then have the opportunity to present and discuss the identified gaps in the topics within the respective domains/themes, and capacity and effectiveness gaps along the chain prevent-detect-respond, as well as gaps with regard to the SRA.
- Based on the results of the gap analysis and input from the consensus meeting with the secretaries, a report on priority research and integrative topics, as well as research areas insufficiently covered by the first round of granted projects will be delivered for further input from the PMT.
- During the preparatory meeting with PMT in May 2018 (see point 3), the report on priority research and integrative topics, and research areas, that are deemed insufficiently covered by the first round of granted projects will be further discussed and validated.

2. Preparatory meeting with domain and theme secretaries

(April 2018, Schiphol Airport, 1 day)

- To discuss and validate the results of the gap analysis of priority research and integrative topics insufficiently covered by the first round of granted projects. Each secretary will have the opportunity to present and discuss the identified gaps in the respective domains/themes.
- To propose a fully justified selection of first round topics to be included again in the prioritization process for the second call for project proposals.

- To discuss and validate the results of the gap analysis with regard to the research areas of the SRA.
- To prepare a draft programme and procedure for topic prioritization for the experts meeting to be held at the RIVM in Bilthoven in June 2018 (see point 4).

3. Preparatory meeting with PMT

(May 2018, location to be defined, 1 day)

- To discuss and validate the report of the gap analysis and the selection of first round topics identified by the secretaries to be (re)included in the prioritization process for the second call for project proposals.
- Selected integrative topics will be subject to an additional selection procedure, which will involve consultation of all partners (WP4).
- To validate the draft programme for the experts meeting in June 2018 (see point 4) and the procedure/criteria, including the weights, for the multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to be used for priority setting. The new procedure/criteria for the prioritization of the topics will have to address:
 - Specific stakeholders' needs (input from WP5 expected in April 2018 with the provisional report on the research and integrative needs of stakeholders), including possible emerging threats.
 - Strategic interactions and possible redundancy with other EU projects/initiatives (input from WP2, task 2.2, with the updated list of projects/initiatives as well as the representation of these projects/initiatives in the One Health EJP matrix to identify possible duplications).
 - For the integrative topics, partners' needs and capacity.
 - Gaps in coverage of specific research areas of the SRA.
 - Enablement of a broad geographical coverage of the second round projects, possibly including also collaborations with external (EU and non-EU) partners at their own costs (WP3/WP4, guidelines will follow).
 - Enablement of integrative actions (e.g. multiple targets for intervention, projects that contribute to the EJP goals of alignment and integration of partner organizations, etc.).

4. Experts meeting

(June 4-5, 2018, RIVM)

- A 2-day meeting involving the WP leaders, 1 national experts per partner organization (including the domain/theme secretaries), and a team of facilitators to identify the new priority research and integrative topics, providing the basis for development of the new SRA and the second One Health EJP call for project proposals.
- A balanced representation from the medical/public health and the veterinary/food safety fields will be strived for.
- National experts will be asked to discuss beforehand with their national Programme Owners the national priorities related to the topics to be prioritized.
- The meeting has the objectives to:
 - Day 1: To narrow down the first round research topics (including those identified as being insufficiently covered by the first round projects) by theme, considering also the needs of the key stakeholders (WP5) and the established strategic links with other relevant EU projects (subtask 2.2 of WP2 and subtask 4.3.1 of WP4) to avoid duplication. This will be done as follows:

- 5 theme-specific working groups including 8 national experts and 1-2 facilitators each (equally balanced between the medical and veterinary fields), led by the respective theme secretaries.
- 1 rapporteur (preferably the secretary) per working group (to report the outcome of the working group session in the plenary session).
- Narrow down the priority research topics per theme, taking into account the raw topics suggested by the national experts for the first round, the gap analysis performed by the secretaries and validated by the PMT, stakeholders' needs (WP5) and information on other EC funded projects and initiatives (WP2).
- In line with the narrow down process, cross-domain priority research topics will be allocated to the most appropriate/prominent domain.
- Outcomes to be reported by the rapporteurs of the 5 working groups.
- Day 2:
 - Session 1: Prioritization by domain of the narrowed research topics.
 - 3 domain-specific working groups including 13 to 14 national experts and 2 to 3 facilitators each (equally balanced between the medical and veterinary fields), led by the respective domain secretaries.
 - 1 rapporteur (preferably the secretary) per working group to report the outcome of the working group session in the plenary session.
 - Priority setting of the research topics identified per domain based on a MCDA procedure - whose criteria were (re)defined during the preparatory meeting with PMT - to be performed in 3 subgroups (1 per domain) of 5 experts (1 expert per theme) each.
 - Session 2: Prioritization of integrative topics.
 - As integrative topics are a bit different in nature from the research projects and have a more developmental focus where there has to be a clear need expressed by the key stakeholders (WP5), and responsibility taken for their development and feasibility by the partners (WP4), their prioritization will be slightly different from the one of the research topics. Before the experts meeting, a list of integrative topics to be prioritized will be compiled based on the input from the gap analysis, potential strategic interactions with other EU projects/initiatives, stakeholders' needs and consultation of the partners. These two latter steps will allow for the ranking of the integrative topics based on needs (stakeholders) and applicability (partners), which will be presented during this session. Final ranking of the integrative topics will be then performed during this session using a restricted MCDA, i.e. a MCDA involving only the secretaries (as there is no need to involve all the experts given the extra input provided by the partners) and having different criteria (defined at the PMT meeting in May) than the MCDA for the research topics.
 - Session 3: Plenary session.
 - Outcomes of the priority research topics to be reported by the rapporteurs of the 3 working groups in a plenary session.
 - Outcomes of the priority integrative topics to be reported by the WP4 leader in a plenary session.
- The meeting will result in an updated list of ranked priority research topics per domain, as well as a list of ranked priority integrative topics.

5. Consultation of the Stakeholders Committee (June 2018)

- In collaboration with WP5, a consultation of the updated list of priority topics by the Stakeholders Committee (SC) will be organized. Other stakeholders may be invited, if considered relevant.

6. Evaluation by the PMT

(June 2018)

- The PMT will evaluate the outcomes of the experts meeting and the consultation of the SC to ensure that the updated lists of priority research and integrative topics are compliant with the pre-defined criteria and the stakeholders' needs.

7. Detailed description of the identified priority topics

(July-August 2018)

- The domain and theme secretaries will provide detailed descriptions of the updated priority topics by using a standard one page format including: 1) objectives; 2) expected results; 3) type and volume of resources needed. The PMT will validate the proposal.
- The descriptions of the set of topics will be submitted to the SSB for the final selection of topics that will be included in the second One Health EJP internal call for project proposals.

8. Validation of priority topics by the Scientific Steering Board (SSB)

(September 2018)

- Ultimately two weeks before the meeting of the SSB, the ranked lists and the descriptions of the priority research and integrative topics will be submitted to the members of the SSB.
- At the SSB meeting in September 2018, the selection of priority research and integrative topics for the second call for proposals will take place following an established protocol.

9. Updating the SRA

(September -December 2018)

- Upon description of the priority topics and their validation by the SSB, the SRA will be updated by the WP2 task leader in collaboration with the theme and domain secretaries.